

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

MEASURES TO ENHANCE THE INVESTMENT APPEAL OF CONSTRUCTION COMPANIES

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Abstract

It has been established that the development of construction companies—as key economic entities influencing the operations of other firms—depends on the application of modern strategic tools, taking into account the influence of various stakeholder groups. There are certain issues concerning the operations of construction companies.

Of particular importance is overcoming the consequences of aggressive military operations. The scope and areas of application of strategic tools in construction enterprises are diminishing. The processes of improving the regulatory framework for investment attractiveness and stakeholder interaction require further refinement. A complex set of unresolved problems has made the research topic regarding the development of measures to ensure the growth of investment attractiveness of construction enterprises highly relevant.

As a result of the research, the objective of developing measures to ensure the growth of investment attractiveness of construction enterprises has been achieved.

Scientific and practical recommendations have been proposed for the development and implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy for enhancing the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises, based on the results of economic and mathematical modelling and forecasting, which has enabled the formulation of measures to boost investment attractiveness.

As a result of the study, theoretical approaches to identifying stakeholders of construction enterprises are proposed: functional, classificatory, transformational, systemic, evaluative and instrumental.

Keywords: investment attractiveness, construction companies, measures, stakeholders, strategy, practical recommendations.

Introduction. The development of construction companies, as key economic actors that influence the operations of other firms, depends on the application of modern strategic tools, taking into account the influence of various stakeholder groups. There are certain problematic issues regarding the operation of construction enterprises (CE). In particular, the directions for the formation and implementation of innovative processes in the construction sector are inadequately defined and supported. The factors of innovative development that influence the operation of construction enterprises are: ensuring the modernisation of fixed assets; the development of energy-saving technologies; the development and application of 'green' technologies; increasing working capital; improving the regulatory and legal framework for the development of the construction sector; financial support for the innovative activities of construction enterprises; the application of financial instruments and mechanisms for the develop-

ment of innovative activities in construction enterprises; and the promotion of an innovation culture [1]. Of particular importance is overcoming the consequences of aggressive military operations. The scope and areas of application for strategic tools within construction enterprises are diminishing. Further refinement is required in the processes of improving the regulatory framework for investment attractiveness (IA) and stakeholder engagement. Consequently, a complex set of unresolved issues has made the topic of this study—concerning the development of measures to ensure the growth of investment attractiveness in construction enterprises—highly relevant.

Justification of existing theoretical approaches. The following types of stakeholders operating in the construction sector in accordance with the relevant regulatory framework have been identified: the client; the consulting engineer; people with reduced mobility; authorities responsible for urban planning;

state architectural and construction control and supervision bodies; bodies responsible for regulatory planning and land development; architectural and construction councils; clients commissioning urban planning documentation; technical administrator of the electronic system in the construction sector; stakeholders responsible for obtaining the information and/or documents required for the preparation of design documentation for the construction and/or technical upgrading of external power supply networks for the client's electrical installations (up to the connection point of the client's electrical installations) and design documentation for the construction of electrical networks for the linear section of the connection, and the specifics of approving such design documentation; owners or managers of construction sites; local authorities; other authorised bodies for urban planning and architecture; chief architects; creative unions of architects; self-regulatory organisations in the field of architectural activity; owners and users of architectural structures; construction companies – manufacturers of construction products; importers of construction products; distributors of construction products; the body responsible for determining technical acceptability; conformity assessment bodies; state market surveillance and state construction control bodies [2–4].

The investment climate is regarded as a comprehensive indicator of the state of enterprises in terms of growth prospects, return on investment and the level of investment risk, which motivates foreign investors to invest [5].

An instrumental approach to determining the investment attractiveness of enterprises has been implemented from the perspective of technologies, mechanisms and means of ensuring it [6].

The investment attractiveness of enterprises is influenced by factors relating to the investment climate: the political situation in the country; the level of economic stability; the regulatory framework governing investment activity; market conditions; the level of development of the domestic market; measures to ensure the efficient functioning of economic sectors; the extent of external influences; and the level of development of intellectual capital [5].

Building on the factor-based approach, investment attractiveness is characterised by factors that influence business operations: political and legal; economic; resource-related; infrastructure-related; market-related; competitive; stakeholder relations; technological; social [7].

The investment attractiveness of enterprises is characterised by their ability to attract investment resources of an appropriate volume and quality, and their capacity for simple and expanded reproduction, with a view to ensuring the sustainable development of production within a socially oriented market economy [8, p. 23].

The following characteristics of investment activities by construction companies have been identified: determining the areas of investment; the development and implementation of investment projects; identifying the parties involved in investment activities; the conduct of investment activities; ensuring state regulation

of investment activities; safeguarding the rights of parties involved in investment activities; the liability of parties involved in investment activities; and determining the conditions for the termination of investment activities [9].

The following approaches to determining the investment potential of enterprises are described:

- identifying indicators for the quantitative assessment of investment attractiveness, taking into account static and dynamic characteristics;
- determining the state of investment activity, taking into account the level of investment attractiveness and activity;
- the intensity of investment activity;
- ensuring investment in production and business activities;
- characterisation of the enterprise's activities;
- the outcome of realising the enterprise's investment opportunities [10, p. 33].

The following classification criteria for a company's strategy have been identified, namely:

- areas of management and the specific features of its implementation;
- the company's operational life cycle;
- market behaviour; securing competitive advantages [11].

In addition, the following strategies are identified: corporate, business, functional and operational [12]. Depending on the approaches used to formulate the strategy and its functional purpose, they are classified as: global strategies, portfolio strategies and functional strategies [12]. It has been determined that a strategy needs to be developed to ensure the long-term operation of enterprises [13]. When formulating a development strategy for construction companies, account is taken of the specific characteristics of their operations and the impact of the construction sector [14, 15].

Consequently, in light of the above, the development of measures to enhance the investment attractiveness of construction companies requires a theoretical basis.

The aim of the study is to develop measures to enhance the investment attractiveness of construction companies.

Main section. The proposed measures to ensure the growth of the investment attractiveness of construction companies focus on increasing the following indicators:

- indicators characterising the impact of the consequences of hostilities on the functioning of construction companies and their participation in overcoming these consequences by 1% through;
- ensuring the completeness and accuracy of construction costs, establishing and maintaining databases of building standards, carrying out standardisation work in the construction sector during martial law, amending and implementing regional development programmes during martial law, amending urban planning documentation during martial law, identifying and taking into account the specific features of applying national standards for construction products, developing and implementing a programme for the comprehensive

restoration of the region or the territory of a local community (or part thereof), ensuring public consultation on draft comprehensive restoration programmes, providing compensation for damaged or destroyed immovable property, applying the procedure for compensation for destroyed immovable property, and compiling a register of damaged property, the effectiveness of construction companies' participation in overcoming the consequences of the Russian Federation's aggression, the application of a rapid response mechanism by the executive bodies of village, settlement and city councils, military administrations, central executive authorities, management bodies and civil protection forces, aimed at eliminating the consequences of the Russian Federation's armed aggression, improving the effectiveness of surveys of damaged properties, organisational and technical measures for preparing to conduct inspections, the commission inspection of damaged facilities by the authorised body, the completeness of documentary support for the dismantling of facilities, the organisation of operations to manage waste from destruction, ensuring the completeness of records of waste from destruction, and the implementation of operations to manage waste from destruction, taking into account the specific features of managing debris during site clearance, taking into account the specific features of managing debris during the dismantling of damaged (destroyed) structures, identifying temporary storage sites for debris, and identifying the specific features of reusing debris;

- indicators characterising the state and operational characteristics of the construction sector, and the economic trajectories of construction enterprises by bringing about fundamental changes in the following areas: the development of technical and organisational aspects of construction, the management of stakeholder interactions, the efficiency of housing construction, the promotion of innovative development in construction, the deregulation of construction activities, growth in construction output indices, total floor area of residential and non-residential buildings, capital investment volumes, current liquidity of the construction enterprises studied, financial autonomy, financial dependence, return on assets of the construction enterprises studied, capital intensity, the current ratio, and the return on net sales of construction products;

- stakeholder indicators by 2% through: improving the effectiveness of stakeholder analysis tools for construction enterprises, ensuring the typology of stakeholders, the effectiveness of stakeholder interaction strategies, and the level of interaction with construction clients, consulting engineers, and people with reduced mobility, authorities responsible for urban planning, state architectural and construction control and supervision bodies, bodies responsible for regulatory and legal planning and land development, architectural and construction councils, clients of urban planning documentation, technical administrators of the electronic system in the construction sector, and stakeholders which ensure the provision of information and/or documents necessary for the preparation of design documentation for the construction and/or technical upgrading of external power supply networks for the client's electrical installations (up to the point of

connection of the client's electrical installations) and design documentation for the construction of the linear section of the connection, as well as the specifics of the approval of such design documentation, external owners or managers of construction sites, local authorities, other authorised bodies for urban planning and architecture, chief architects, creative associations of architects, self-regulatory organisations in the field of architectural activity, external owners and users of architectural structures, construction companies – manufacturers of construction products, importers of construction products, distributors of construction products, bodies responsible for determining technical acceptability, conformity assessment bodies, bodies responsible for state market surveillance and state construction control, central government bodies, local government bodies, organisations providing external information support to construction companies, social institutions, external financial institutions and organisations, external supervisory bodies (National Police of Ukraine, Security Service of Ukraine, Armed Forces of Ukraine, State Tax Service of Ukraine, State Customs Service, State Audit Service), other external stakeholders, internal representatives of construction company management bodies, internal owners of construction enterprises, construction enterprise workers, representatives of internal regulatory bodies of construction enterprises, internal financial departments of construction enterprises, representatives responsible for the formulation and implementation of construction enterprises' information policy, representatives responsible for the formulation and implementation of construction enterprises' social policy, and other internal stakeholders;

- indicators characterising the directions and specific features of investment activity, based on the implementation of fundamental changes achieved through: the development and implementation of a construction enterprise's development strategy; the comprehensive establishment of legal, financial, material and intellectual support; the development of programmes, projects and development plans; the building of investment capacity; the realisation of investment potential; monitoring, evaluation, adjustment of the implementation of investment projects, ensuring the investment activity of construction enterprises, and stakeholder engagement to support the investment activities of construction enterprises;

- environmental indicators with a 1% increase through: the participation of construction enterprises in state-funded and other environmental programmes, the observance of citizens' environmental rights, the impact of environmental protection management on the construction sector, the influence of environmental protection NGOs on the functioning of the construction sector, ensuring environmental monitoring for the functioning of the construction sector, taking into account the results of state registration of facilities that have a harmful impact on the state of the environment, utilising information on the state of the environment (environmental information), improving the level of environmental information provision in the construction sector, the use of environmental technologies at construction enterprises, compliance with environmental

standards at construction enterprises, ensuring environmental protection oversight for the operation of construction enterprises, ensuring public oversight in the field of environmental protection for the operation of construction enterprises, implementation of economic measures to ensure environmental protection for the operation of construction enterprises, funding of environmental protection measures for the operation of construction enterprises, ensuring environmental safety in the construction sector, effective management of construction waste, development and use of «green» construction tools, ensuring funding for mechanisms to support «green» construction, the level of support for «green» construction, ensuring the development of «green» construction, state regulation of «green» construction, determining compensation for environmental impact, state control, ensuring the certification of «green» construction projects, applying economic incentives for «green» construction, implementation of regional and local «green» construction programmes, participation of construction companies in regional and local «green» construction programmes, public awareness-raising regarding the development and implementation of regional and local «green» construction programmes, ensuring international cooperation in the field of «green» construction, green recovery, ensuring sustainability in the recovery process, ensuring sustainable (green) investment, the implementation of sustainable (green) recovery measures, governance in the recovery process, ensuring the recovery of individual sites and territories, state planning for «green» recovery, ensuring the monitoring of the implementation of «green» recovery programmes, the implementation of state policy in the field of ensuring the energy efficiency of buildings, information support for the energy efficiency of buildings, ensuring the energy efficiency of buildings, ensuring compliance with energy efficiency requirements for buildings at construction enterprises, the energy efficiency of buildings at construction enterprises, the effectiveness of energy audits of buildings at construction enterprises, the certification of persons intending to carry out energy efficiency certification activities, energy audits of buildings and inspections of technical installations, the effectiveness of self-regulatory organisations in the field of building energy efficiency, the effectiveness of building energy auditors, thermal modernisation and promotion of improved building energy efficiency, ensuring building energy efficiency through energy management systems, inspections of a building's technical installations, independent monitoring of energy certificates and reports on the results of inspections of technical installations, implementation of the National Plan to increase the number of buildings with near-zero energy consumption, development and implementation of a strategy for the thermal modernisation of buildings, provision of funding for thermal modernisation and energy efficiency measures, liability for breaches of legislation in the field of ensuring the energy efficiency of buildings;

– significant changes in ensuring the security of construction enterprises based on: the implementation of state policy in the fields of national security and defence; the impact of state policy in the fields of national

security and defence on the functioning of construction enterprises; democratic civilian oversight; the provision of support to the security and defence sector; coordination in the fields of national security and defence; planning in the field of national security and defence; the implementation of the national security strategy, the implementation of the military security strategy, the implementation of Ukraine's public security and civil protection strategy, the implementation of the strategy for the development of Ukraine's defence-industrial complex, the implementation of Ukraine's cybersecurity strategy, the implementation of the strategy for integrated management of Ukraine's state border, the development of the national intelligence programme, the implementation of state programmes in the fields of national security and defence, financial support for the security and defence sector, economic, financial, information security, ensuring that the minimum subsistence level meets social standards, the realisation of the right to financial support in the event of unemployment and social services; vocational training or retraining, and professional development in institutions of vocational (vocational-technical), pre-higher and higher education, at construction enterprises; the provision to employers who employ citizens, in particular those with additional guarantees regarding employment assistance, of compensation in accordance with Article 26 of the Law of Ukraine «On Employment» at construction enterprises; the implementation of other social programmes at construction enterprises; the prevention of insured events; the effective management of unemployment insurance, ensuring supervision in the field of unemployment insurance, the formation and use of unemployment insurance funds, material support in the event of unemployment, ensuring the rights, duties and responsibilities of stakeholders when interacting with construction enterprises, pension provision, the formation and application of elements of the system and classification of social standards, the definition and application of state social standards and norms, the provision of state social guarantees, the financial provision for the implementation of state social standards, the provision of compulsory state social insurance, the rights, duties and responsibilities of stakeholders when interacting with construction companies in the field of compulsory compulsory state social insurance, improving the effectiveness of compulsory state social insurance against unemployment, compulsory state social insurance against accidents at work and occupational diseases resulting in loss of working capacity, ensuring control and supervision in the field of social insurance, social protection of labour veterans and other elderly citizens in Ukraine, social and legal protection of military personnel and their families, social protection of children of war, collection and accounting of the single contribution for compulsory state social insurance, state assistance to families with children, state social assistance to persons not entitled to a pension, and persons with disabilities, state social assistance to low-income families, state social assistance to persons with disabilities since childhood and children with disabilities, social protection of citizens affected by the Chernobyl disaster, social protection of homeless persons

and street children, and the provision of other social services;

- increasing the level of generation and utilisation of investment and innovation resources in construction enterprises through: the generation and utilisation of investment resources from domestic stakeholders in construction enterprises, the generation and utilisation of investment resources from foreign stakeholders in construction enterprises, ensuring state regulation in the field of innovation, the development and implementation of innovative projects, the development and use of innovative products, the effective operation of innovative enterprises, the provision of financial support for innovative activities at construction enterprises, international cooperation in the field of innovative activities, the formulation and implementation of strategic directions for the development of innovation, ensuring the monitoring of the implementation of priority areas of innovation, the functioning of the national innovation ecosystem, and the implementation of the strategy for the development of the innovation sector.

Conclusions. Scientific and practical recommendations are proposed for the development and implementation of a stakeholder-oriented strategy for enhancing the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises, based on the results of economic and mathematical modelling and forecasting, which has enabled the formulation of measures to increase the investment attractiveness of construction enterprises.

As a result of the study, theoretical approaches to identifying stakeholders of construction enterprises are proposed:

- functional: the directions and characteristics of interaction between construction enterprise stakeholders are identified;
- classification-based: the types of stakeholders of construction enterprises are characterised;
- transformational: changes occurring in the process of interaction between construction enterprise stakeholders are identified;
- systemic: stakeholders are considered as elements of a complex production and economic system of construction enterprise operations, whose interaction leads to positive changes and the development of construction enterprises;
- evaluative: focuses on methods and models for assessing the level of interaction among stakeholders in construction enterprises;
- instrumental: characterises the tools that facilitate interaction among stakeholders.

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